

HISTORICAL SOCIETIES AND PRESERVATION

Gunilla Jensen

*Transpower
New Zealand*
Gunilla.Jensen@Transpower.co.nz
[ORCID 0009-0004-9193-813X](https://orcid.org/0009-0004-9193-813X)

Michael Williams

*Transpower
New Zealand*
Michael.Williams@Transpower.co.nz
[ORCID 0009-0009-2750-6320](https://orcid.org/0009-0009-2750-6320)

Abstract – Grid Heritage collects historic equipment, film footage, photographs and documents relating to electricity transmission in New Zealand. Transpower NZ Ltd builds, maintains, and operates the high voltage electricity transmission grid. Transpower’s Disposal Schedule lists “Discharge” as an option for disposal of records of no national archival value to Grid Heritage. Historical societies, like Grid Heritage, may already be experiencing challenges with their physical records. Whilst receiving electronic records will create further challenges for them, they do have the opportunity to prepare themselves for potentially receiving digital media. This poster will open for discussion on digital preservation for a small historical society.

Submission Type – Poster.

Keywords – Community, People Capacity, Historical Societies, Electricity Transmission

Conference Topics – Haerenga – Journey

I. INTRODUCTION

Grid Heritage[1] collects historic equipment, film footage, photographs and documents relating to electricity transmission in New Zealand. Their aim is to record the historic development of the New Zealand high voltage electricity grid since 1888. Grid Heritage doesn’t currently have a collection policy for digital content.

Grid Heritage is run by volunteers and supported by Transpower NZ, Power Systems Consultants (PSC) and Massey University Museum Studies Group.

Transpower NZ Ltd builds, maintains, and operates the high voltage electricity transmission

grid that connects generators of electricity with users around New Zealand.

Transpower’s Retention and Disposal Schedule [2] applies to information and records pertaining to the functions of Transpower.

Seven sub-classes of records within the Transpower Disposal Schedule lists discharge as an option for disposal. Use of the discharge option as a disposal action is intended to allow for discharge of records of no national archival value to Grid Heritage. If Grid Heritage do not want the records, when offered, they will instead be destroyed.

By providing a discharge option to Grid Heritage, Transpower can acknowledge that certain records may not be deemed to have archival value, as it applies to a national archival institution, but may still have some historic interest to those who are enthusiasts and historians on matters of electricity transmission in New Zealand. A formal process is in place between Transpower and Grid Heritage to support the discharge process.

The records relating to specific transmission assets or equipment that are of value to Grid Heritage because they may already hold a sample of the actual piece of equipment, or historic accounts relating to the use of the equipment. These digital records come in a large range of formats from Microsoft Office files to specific file formats for specialised systems. SharePoint was implemented as Transpower’s primary document management system in 2014, with the switch from shared networks drives to SharePoint as the primary

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Gunilla Jensen is an Information Management Advisor at Transpower New Zealand. Gunilla provides subject matter expertise in information management and act as a champion for effective creation and maintenance of information. Prior to Transpower, Gunilla has been a records manager and librarian for more than 20 years.

Michael Williams works as an Information Management Advisor at Transpower New Zealand, the nation's grid and electricity system operator. He has over 25 years of experience in information management and is interested in the preservation of information in areas that traditionally receive less attention.

repository made in the following years. A project will be undertaken to implement disposal across relevant non-current paper-based and digital information and records once the new Transpower disposal schedule is approved by Archives New Zealand in 2025.

Previously, historical societies only needed to handle physical artefacts including documents and maps. Now, the documents and maps are in digital format. This presents new challenges to preserving them. Especially, for small historical societies like Grid Heritage that are unlikely to have the relevant skills, software and appropriate storage to preserve digital content.

However, they can become aware of the challenges and prepare themselves for receiving electronic records in the future. This is an opportunity for Grid Heritage to develop their own archival and preservation practices.

To the authors' knowledge, there are currently no resources or expertise available to assist Grid Heritage in meeting these digital preservation challenges. Grid Heritage will have to consider this as part of their future planning process.

This poster will open for discussion and pose questions on how a small historical society like Grid Heritage can prepare themselves for receiving electronic records and preserving digital formats especially different formats such as digital maps and digital drawings? What resources (or lack of resources) are available for them? How does an amateur historical society obtain the necessary expertise that is required to properly preserve its historical records?

II. CONCLUSION

The value of digital preservation for historical societies such as Grid Heritage is important.

The transition from paper-based records to digital formats presents challenges and opportunities for Grid Heritage. By proactively preparing to receive digital records, they can safeguard the rich history of New Zealand's electricity transmission for future generations

REFERENCES

- [1] Grid Heritage. <https://www.gridheritage.org.nz/>
- [2] Transpower Disposal Schedule (DA552).

